

Director's Note: The Making of Colder (2022)

By Shayaan Aslam Bhat aka. Shen B (Artist, Co-Director)

Colder (music video) began as a personal experiment to tell a science fiction story without waiting for resources, approval, or a large crew. I wanted to prove to myself, and others, that we don't need a studio-sized budget to explore futuristic sci-fi worlds. Sometimes, all it takes is conviction, a camera, and a little madness.

We were a three-person production crew. I wrote the concept, designed the costumes, handled makeup, built the props, did the sound design, produced the music, performed the vocals, acted in the video, and created the artwork for the song, all by myself. My closest collaborator, Wikki Koul, directed, shot, edited, and did the VFX. My cousin Shahaan Bhat, who has no background in filmmaking, still came along to support us and shot behind-the-scenes photos and videos while helping carry equipment through snow-covered terrain. Danish Tak supported us as producers, helping with whatever funds and resources we needed to keep the project moving.

We travelled to Patnitop, 105 kilometres from Jammu city, Jammu & Kashmir, India, chasing snowfall based on weather forecasts. The forecast failed, delaying the shoot and forcing us to compress our three-day plan into just two days of shooting. It was the first time any of us had faced a blizzard. The temperature dropped to -3°C , and for the first time, I knew what it felt like to lose sensation in my ears, nose, and fingertips, because none of us had proper snow gear or prior experience.

The snowstorm kept returning in phases, but in one rare moment of stillness, the sky opened up, the clouds turned theatrical, the light fell evenly, and the snow-covered surroundings looked quietly surreal. I turned to Wikki and said, “When God lights up a scene, cinematographers just watch and learn.” That was his cue to stop worrying about our entry-level camera and keep rolling. By then, we’d also learned that in sub-zero temperatures, camera batteries drain rapidly. To avoid interruptions, we connected a power bank directly to the camera while shooting, and I honestly can’t thank Sony enough for enabling that feature. It saved us.

I was determined to build everything from scratch. The distressing of props and costumes turned out to be the most fun part. It’s easier to make a prop look new, but ageing it, dirtying it, making it feel like it’s survived a world war, that takes storytelling. One day, I connected an LED light directly to a battery, and it blew up. I kept trying different battery sizes, and it still burned out. Coming from a humanities background, I had to pause and learn a bit of physics. I finally figured out how to use a capacitor and solder a basic circuit. That day, I told myself, this is the beauty of art. One day, it turns you into an actor, the next day into a technician.

The time machine prop, gauntlets, cloaks, and makeup were all designed with intent. Even the sketchbooks in the film are different across timelines; the future sketches are done in charcoal, symbolising the use of burnt coal. Every little piece added to the character’s evolution.

Jammu remains underrepresented in visual culture, often seen only as a gateway to Kashmir. I’ve always felt Jammu is like me, lesser known, but no less. This was our way of putting it on the map, of showing that snow-laden forests and apocalyptic quiet can be found here too.

Post-production took a year. Just me and Wikki, working late nights, balancing other projects and responsibilities. I would often get impatient with Wikki’s obsession over minute VFX details. Once I asked, “Who’s going to notice this?” He replied, “I will. And that’s what matters.” That is one thing that surely stuck with me.

When I made *Colder*, I wasn’t part of academia. I was just a storyteller with a deep love for sci-fi. That’s why this Director’s Note comes later, not because the reflection was delayed, but because the story is still teaching me things.

Colder wasn’t just a music video. It was a commitment to the idea that creativity can be tactical, instinctive, and beautifully handmade. You don’t need permission to build worlds. You just need a little ‘madness’.

Shayaan Aslam Bhat
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